

Effect of salinity levels (0 [control] and 100 mol NaCl) (3 wk stress) on Zn and P concentrations in shoot and root of 4 rice varieties and lines.^aFaisalabad, Pakistan.

Variety or line	Fresh wt (g/plant)		Zn ²⁺ (mg/kg dry wt)		P (%)		Zn ²⁺ :P	
	0	100	0	100	0	100	0	100
	Shoot							
Basmati 370	19.25 a	3.99 c (21)	32.7 d	43.3 b-d	0.224 e	0.281 b	1.46 × 10 ⁻²	1.54 × 10 ⁻²
NIAB6	19.91 a	7.81 b (39)	41.0 cd	71.3 a	0.163	0.231 d	2.51 × 10 ⁻²	3.09 × 10 ⁻²
BG402-4	16.52 a	5.94 bc (36)	37.7 d	50.7 b	0.216	0.267 c	1.75 × 10 ⁻²	1.90 × 10 ⁻²
IR1561	19.50 a	2.96 d (15)	43.3 b-d	51.3 bc	0.231 d	0.287 a	1.87 × 10 ⁻²	1.79 × 10 ⁻²
Mean	18.80 A	5.18 B	38.7 B	54.7 A	0.208 B	0.266 A	1.64 × 10 ⁻²	2.68 × 10 ⁻²
	Root							
Basmati 370	21.12 ab	5.98 d (28)	43.3 b	43.3 b	0.131 d	0.157 b	3.30 × 10 ⁻²	2.76 × 10 ⁻²
NIAB6	19.69 ab	9.46 c (48)	58.7 a	62.3 a	0.127 d	0.157 b	4.62 × 10 ⁻²	3.97 × 10 ⁻²
BG402-4	18.82 b	10.13 c (54)	56.0 a	56.7 a	0.131 c	0.152 a	4.27 × 10 ⁻²	3.73 × 10 ⁻²
IR1561	23.12 a	4.10 d (18)	59.7 a	55.0 a	0.141 c	0.195 a	4.23 × 10 ⁻²	2.82 × 10 ⁻²
Mean	20.55 A	7.42 B	54.4 A	53.3 A	0.132 B	0.165 A	4.10 × 10 ⁻²	3.32 × 10 ⁻²

^aMeans with different letters differ significantly by DMRT (P = 0.05). The Zn²⁺: P ratio is calculated when the concentration of Zn and P is in percent. Values in the parentheses represent percentages of respective controls.

various plant tissues, ionic balance, osmotic adjustment, etc.) are related to a plant's salt tolerance. Many workers have used these physiological traits to screen rice genotypes for salt tolerance. We determined the effect of external salinity on Zn and P concentrations in shoot and root. Seedlings of four rice varieties were transferred at 14 d to foam-plugged holes (1 cm diam) in thermopal sheets floating on Yoshida nutrient solution at two salinity levels: 0

and 100 mol NaCl in plastic tubs. Plants were harvested after 3 wk, separated into shoot and root, dried, and Zn and P contents determined.

Zn²⁺ concentration in the shoot increased significantly with external salinity of 100 mol NaCl; in the root, it was not affected by salt stress (see table). Zn concentration in the shoot of salt-tolerant NIAB6 was significantly higher than in the other varieties. Zn concentration in roots of NIAB6 was

significantly higher than that of Basmati 370 (which had the lowest Zn²⁺ concentration in shoot and root).

Salt-sensitive IR1561 had significantly higher P concentration in shoot and root than all other varieties; salt-tolerant NIAB6 had significantly lower shoot P concentration than all other varieties.

Zn:P ratios in shoot and root were highest in NIAB6 and lowest in Basmati 370 with and without salt stress. These ratios were also low in IR1561. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Two modern photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties for Bangladesh

M. A. Kabir and N. M. Miah, Plant Breeding Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

BRRI recently released modern photoperiod-sensitive varieties BR22 and BR23 for T. aman season in Bangladesh.

BR22 was developed from Nizersail/BR51-46-5; BR23 was derived from DA29/ BR4. Both varieties are suitable for late planting in T. aman. Yield potential and disease reactions are comparable to those of existing modern

Grain yield and plant height of 2 new varieties for Bangladesh.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	
		1st planting	2d planting
BR22	115	4.4	3.4
BR23	120	4.6	3.7
BR11 (check)	110	3.8	1.3
Nizersail (local check)	132	3.1	2.6

^aAverage of 3 yr at 4 regional stations. 1st planting: 4-15 Aug with 30-d-old seedlings, 2d planting: 15-22 Sep with 40-d-old seedlings.

varieties, but the new varieties yield more than 1 t higher in late plantings (see table).

BR22 has medium bold grain with intermediate amylose content and

moderate resistance to tungro (RTV), bacterial leaf blight, sheath rot, sheath blight (ShB), and blast.

BR23 has long slender grain with intermediate amylose content and moderate resistance to RTV, stem rot, ShB, and submergence tolerance. □

RAU4045-2A — a very short duration cultivar for harsh upland environments

S. C. Prasad, Plant Breeding and Genetics Department, Birsa Agricultural University, Kanke, Ranchi; and J. B. Tomar, NBPGR Regional Station, Ranchi, India

RAU4045-2A (IET9790), a semidwarf variety derived from Fine Gora/ IET2832, has resistance to brown spot and grain discoloration and

Table 1. Yield of RAU4045-2A (IET9790) in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project during 1985 and 1986.

Variety	1985 yield (t/ha)							1986 yield (t/ha)					
	Titabar	Hazaribagh	Kanke	Faizabad	Coimbatore	Pondicherry	Mean	Chiplima	Arudhatinagar	Kanke	Faizabad	Mean	Mean days to 50% flowering
RAU4045-2A	1.6	3.7	3.5	3.5	5.0	4.4	3.6	1.7	2.5	4.3	3.6	3.0	59
Akashi (national check)	1.2	2.2	2.7	3.2	5.0	4.0	3.0	1.2	2.4	3.2	3.5	2.6	68
Cauvery	1.3	1.8	1.7	2.6	4.8	3.9	2.7	0.6	2.4	1.5	1.9	1.6	70
Local check	—	1.3	1.9	2.7	5.0	4.2	2.5	1.3	2.0	1.9	3.2	2.1	71
		(Brown Gora)	(Brown Gora)										
LSD (0.05)								0.7	0.7	0.7	0.5		

moderate resistance to bacterial blight and blast. It has a very short duration (80-85 d) and early vegetative vigor. It can survive a drought at the vegetative stage and is highly suited to drought-prone upland areas.

It has up to 125 grains/panicle and 1,000-grain weight is 23 g. Grain is short bold with high hulling (76%), milling (72%), and head rice recovery (63%). It has intermediate gelatinization temperature and gel consistency.

Mean yields of RAU4045-2A in regional experiments 1983-86 were 3.5 t/ha compared to Akashi, 2.4 t/ha, and Brown Gora, 2.1 t/ha.

In 1983-85 dryland testing, it yielded an average 2.5 t/ha against checks Bala (2.3 t/ha), Brown Gora (2.3 t/ha), and

Table 2. Average yields of RAU4045-2A in minikit testing in plateau region of Bihar, 1985-86.

District	Minikits (no.)	Average yield (t/ha)		Increase over Local Gora (%)
		RAU4045-2A	Local Gora	
Ranchi	61	1.6	1.3	23
Hazaribagh	45	2.1	1.7	24
Giridih	17	1.2	1.0	20
Palamau	28	1.5	1.2	25
Dhanbad	18	2.4	1.5	60
Total	169	1.8	1.3	31

Kiran (1.9 t/ha). In All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project experiments 1985, it yielded 3.6 t/ha over six locations, better than three other varieties; in 1986, it outyielded three other varieties, with a mean yield of 3.0 t/ha over four locations (Table 1).

In 1985-86 tests (169) RAU4045-2A, mean yield was 1.8 t/ha, compared to 1.34 t/ha for local Gora (Table 2). Mean yield in the International Rice Testing Program trials was 3.4 t/ha over 34 locations in 1982 and 3.5 t/ha over 56 locations in 1983. □

Sachiminori — a fine quality rice cultivar

Sheng Jinshan, Institute of Crop Germplasm Resources, Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, China

Sachiminori, a japonica introduced from Japan in 1982, has very high tillering ability, panicles/plant, and spikelet fertility, 1,000-grain weight of 26 g, and yields 6-7 t/ha. Grain quality is fine, with acceptable flavor. Percentage of brown rice is 82 and milled rice, 72-76. Sachiminori is highly resistant to blast and tolerant of drought, and has wide adaptability. When grown under the same conditions, inputs for Sachiminori are lower, yield higher and more stable,

and profit higher than those of most other cultivars.

In 1988, in the region that includes Beijing, Tianjing, and Hebei Provinces, more than 7,000 ha were planted to Sachiminori (renamed Xing Shi). In

recent years, eight other provinces have introduced Xing Shi, changing the early season cultivar choice from the original hsien (indica) rices to keng (japonica) rices. □

Stored grain infestation by Angoumois grain moth (AGM) in resistant and susceptible rice varieties

K. N. Ragumoorthi and K. Gunathilagaraj, Agricultural Entomology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied infestation by AGM *Sitotrogu cerealella* (Olivier) in the resistant CO 32 and susceptible CO 44 rice varieties in the insectary. Mylar film sheet cylinders (30 cm × 6 cm) were divided into 10 cross-sections, each 1 cm deep. Separate cylinders (in three replications) were filled with grains of CO 32 and CO 44 (number of grains in a section average 1,011). AGM eggs in a